

EFFECTIVENESS OF READING COMPREHENSION SKILL

ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM ON THE ACHIEVEMENT OF READING

COMPREHENSION AMONG THE BOYS AND GIRLS

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Abstract

Reading comprehension is an intentional and active part of reading and takes place before, during and after you read something. An attempt was made to study the effectiveness of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on Academic Achievement in English. An experimental method was used for this study. A single group designed was used to compare the effect of Reading Comprehension skill Enhancement Program on Academic Achievement in English. For the present study, stratified random technique was used to select the students, teachers and headmasters from different state secondary schools. In the present study 120 state secondary schools were randomly selected from S. G. Boys and Girls High School Paratwada. For the present study, 600 male and female teachers, and 60 Headmasters were selected randomly. The study revealed that there is significant effect of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on the achievement of reading comprehension among the Boys and Girls.

Keywords: Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program

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Introduction: Communicative approach to teaching and learning English has been a significant development; at present, it is used worldwide in teaching and learning English. Instead of grammar-based approach, practice-based learning is considered important in recent theoretical approaches. This practice covers training of all four basic skills- listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Success of the teaching of English through communicative approach depends entirely on the practice of these skills. Teaching of reading, therefore, needs special attention from the experts and professionals for a meaningful higher education in the country.

According to RAND Reading Study Group (2002), comprehension is the process of eliciting and making meaning through interaction and involvement with written language. McNamara and Magliano (2009) emphasized that this process is a task of both reader and text factors that happen within a larger social context. Duke (2003) stated that comprehension is a process in which readers make meaning by interacting with text through the combination of prior knowledge and previous experience, information in the text, and the views of readers related to the text.

Kintsch (1998) and van Dijk and Kintsch (1983) defined reading comprehension as the process of creating meaning from text. The purpose is to get an understanding of the text rather than to acquire meaning from individual words or sentences. The outcome of reading comprehension is the mental representation of a text meaning that is combined with the readers' previous knowledge. This is called a mental model (Johnson-Laird, 1983) or a situation model (Kintsch, 1998). This model defines what has been learned (RAND Reading And Study Group, 2002). Keenan, Betjemann, and Olson (2008) expressed that reading comprehension needs the successful expansion and arrangement of a lot of lower-and higher-level processes and skills. Accordingly, there are many sources for possible comprehension break and these sources are different based on the skill levels and age of readers.

Reviews of Related Literature:

The investigators have attempted to note down some points which are relevant to the study on previous literature and a theoretical overview of the study.

Karen L. Sanford (2015) University of San Francisco, has conducted the research on the topic of "Factors that Affect the Reading Comprehension of Secondary Students with Disabilities". Objectives of the research: 1. To find out the factors that affect the Reading Comprehension of Secondary Students with Disabilities. Sample: 158 SWD in grades 9 to 12 attending two large urban northern California high schools Method: Experimental, Findings were: 1. of the motivation-to read factors, extrinsic motivation had a statistically significant negative relationship with reading comprehension indicating that internally motivated students had higher reading comprehension ability. 2. Intrinsic motivation was also a significant contributor to reading comprehension when the affective factors were regressed onto reading comprehension. 3. Differences in the relative importance of the cognitive components between low- and high-comprehends were also noted suggesting that high-comprehends had more internalized reading abilities than low-comprehends. **Sungyoon Lee (2021)** undertaken a study "Exploring the Associations between Reading Skills and Eye Movements in Elementary

Children’s Silent Sentence Reading” with the objective to investigate the associations between elementary students’ reading skills and their online reading (i.e., real-time reading) behaviors during silent sentence processing. Thirty-five students participated in this study and their eye movements were recorded during sentence reading tasks. The effects of students’ reading skills measured by traditional standardized measures were investigated for widely-used eye tracking measures such as first fixation duration, gaze duration, regression path duration, total duration, word skipping, fixation count, and regression frequency. The eye tracking measures were chosen to represent early/late cognitive processes and temporal/spatial gaze behaviors. Linear mixed-effects regression analyses revealed that children’s performances in reading skills predict most of the eye tracking measures. **Elena Cueva (2022)** studied “Reading Comprehension in Both Spanish and English as a Foreign Language by High School Spanish Students” with objective to explore the linguistic abilities that determine reading comprehension in Spanish (L1) and in English (L2) in Secondary Education students. To do this, 73 Secondary Education Students (1st and 3rd year) participated in this study. The students carried out a battery of tasks in English and Spanish, all of them related to reading comprehension (expository text) and different linguistic skills, which included syntactic awareness tasks, synonymy judgment tasks (vocabulary), and morphological awareness tasks. The results indicated a positive correlation between linguistic competencies in both languages (indicating a transfer effect between languages), which were determined by school year, with a lower performance in the 1st year than in the 3rd year. Moreover, we found more skills with correlations in English reading comprehension than in Spanish. Finally, reading comprehension in L1 was mainly explained English reading comprehension, while English reading comprehension was predicted by grade, and syntactic awareness, as well as Spanish reading comprehension. This could be explained by the different levels of exposure to L1 and L2 of sample subjects, as the linguistic variables have different influences on the reading comprehension of both languages.

From the above reviews, the present Research problem is unique from the above reviews because the researcher thinks that such type of research has not undertaken by anybody on the Development of Reading comprehension Enhancement Program for English and its Effectiveness on the Academic Achievement of Secondary level students. Researcher developed Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program and studied its effectiveness on Academic Achievement in English. This program is totally based on the Question Paper

Format of Maharashtra State Board of Education, Pune. Hence, the present research problem is unique.

Objectives of the Study: The study was undertaken with the following objectives in view

- To study the effectiveness of Reading Comprehension skill Enhancement Program on Academic Achievement in English.
- To Compare the Academic Achievement of boys and girls students in Reading Comprehension skill of IX standard students.
- To know the views of Headmaster towards Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program for the students of IX standard.

Hypothesis: The Null Hypothesis of the present study was as follows:

There is no significant effect of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on the academic achievement of Boys and Girls of IX standard in English subject.

Methodology of the Study:

An experimental method was used for this study. A single group designed was used to compare the effect of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on Academic Achievement in English. For the present study, stratified random technique was used to select the students, teachers and headmasters from different state secondary schools. In the present study, 120 state secondary schools were randomly selected from S. G. Boys and Girls High School Paratwada. For the present study, 60 Headmasters were selected randomly.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

The analysis of present data was done by using an inferential statistical techniques and percentage. The analysis and interpretation of effectiveness of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on Academic Achievement in English has been reasonably presented in the following table.

Mean difference in Pre and Post-test achievement of Boys and Girls in Reading Comprehension

Groups	Girls N	Mean M	Standard Deviation SD	Standard Error SE	Obtained t Value	Level of Significance 0.01
Pre Test Boys & Girls	120	7.36	3.432			
Post Test Boys & Girls	120	11.00	2.736	0.321	11.339	Significant

Ref: The figures in the above table are based on the field data collected; If $df = 238$ then table t- value at 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance are 1.96 and 2.58 respectively and $r = 0.367421$.

From the above table, it is observed that the mean score in post-test obtained by Boys and Girls in different aspects of reading comprehension (11.00) is higher than that of mean score obtained in pre-test (7.36). Further, it is revealed that the obtained t-value (11.339) is more than the table value at 0.01 level of significance indicates that the mean difference in this comparison is significant. Therefore, there exists statistically significant difference between the Pre and Post-test mean achievement scores of Boys and Girls in reading comprehension. Hence formulated null hypothesis is rejected at 0.01 level of significance. It showed that there is significant effect of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on the achievement of reading comprehension among the Boys and Girls.

Findings:

On the basis of analysis and interpretation of the field data and the analysis of interview of headmasters; the following findings have been drawn:

- There is significant effect of Reading Comprehension Skill Enhancement Program on the achievement of reading comprehension among the Boys and Girls.
- The academic performance of girls is better than boys in reading comprehension.
- On the basis of achievement test results, it is found that the secondary level students have problems in reading comprehension like unable to do the skimming and scanning properly, unable to do the detailed reading, failed to find the contextual vocabulary and grammar, unable to write the answers to the personal response questions. i.e. unable to do the prediction.
- Most of teachers celebrate Saturday as an English Day in their school. They arrange the activities related to reading comprehension skills.
- 75% Headmaster organize the guest lectures for enhancement of language skills in English.

Conclusion: The present study refers to the needs of reading comprehension skills for the secondary level students and finds out that students are unprogressive in reading comprehension such as their efficiency is low in understanding the contextual vocabulary and grammar, can't read rapidly in order to get a general idea, can't find specific information from the passage. At the same time the study has also proved that the teachers and teaching methods are mostly responsible for the poor proficiency in reading comprehension.

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